

EMP-LAC

Scenario analysis of electric and hybrid mobility pathways for light-duty transport in Ecuador

- Mónica López, Programa de las Naciones Unidas para el Desarrollo, Ecuador
- Daniel Hidalgo, Universidad Central del Ecuador

Keywords:

Transport decarbonization; light-duty vehicles; electric vehicles; hybrid vehicles; Ecuador; NDC; OSeMOSYS; electricity demand; energy system modelling

Acknowledgements

This report was developed as part of the Energy Modelling Platform for Latin America and the Caribbean (EMP-LAC) 2026 capacity building process, with technical support from trainers Fernando Plaza and Guillermo Fernández, as well as support from the broader energy modelling community

The authors gratefully acknowledge Climate Compatible Growth, Universidad Politécnica Nacional and the British Embassy in Ecuador for organizing EMP-LAC 2026 and facilitating this learning and modelling process.

This material has been produced with support from the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) programme. CCG is funded by UK aid from the UK government. However, the views expressed herein do not necessarily reflect the UK government's official policies.

Executive Summary

Ecuador's transport sector is one of the main sources of greenhouse gas emissions within the national energy sector, making light-duty vehicle decarbonization a relevant mitigation priority for the country's Second Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) for 2026–2035. This study evaluates alternative mobility transition pathways using OSeMOSYS through MUJO, focusing on the role of battery electric vehicles (BEVs) and hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs) in reducing fossil fuel consumption, transport emissions, energy demand, and fuel import dependence between 2022 and 2050.

Three scenarios are analyzed. The BAU scenario represents the baseline pathway under current trends, without additional electrification targets. The ENEM scenario follows Ecuador's National Electromobility Strategy, assuming stronger BEV deployment in line with national electromobility targets, while also considering HEVs as a complementary technology. The HEV scenario explores a slower BEV deployment pathway, where hybrid vehicles play a stronger transition role in reducing gasoline consumption and direct CO₂ emissions under possible infrastructure, market, or electricity supply constraints.

The results show that both ENEM and HEV will reduce emissions compared with BAU by 2035. BAU reaches 28.08 MtCO₂e, while ENEM reaches 26.48 MtCO₂e, equivalent to a reduction of 1.60 MtCO₂e and a 15% contribution to the NDC conditional target. HEV also remains below BAU, reaching 27.41 MtCO₂e, with a reduction of 0.67 MtCO₂e and a 6% contribution to the NDC conditional target. Over the 2022–2050 period, ENEM reduces cumulative energy demand by 759.34 PJ, or 12.14%, while HEV reduces it by 383.97 PJ, or 6.14%, compared with BAU. The electricity supply results show that hydropower remains the backbone of clean generation, increasing from 88.7 PJ in 2022 to 123.9 PJ in 2050, while solar energy shows the strongest growth, reaching 78.9 PJ in ENEM, 72.5 PJ in HEV, and 70.6 PJ in BAU by 2050. Fuel import results indicate that fossil fuel dependence remains relevant, although transition scenarios reduce gasoline imports: by 2050, gasoline imports reach 327.8 PJ in BAU, compared with 260.9 PJ in ENEM and 299.9 PJ in HEV. Overall, ENEM provides the strongest long-term decarbonization pathway, while HEVs can serve as a complementary transition technology as Ecuador expands charging infrastructure, strengthens power system readiness, and advances toward sustainable mobility.

1. Introduction

Ecuador's transport sector is one of the main contributors to national greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions within energy sector according to the Ecuador's latest national GHG inventory¹. The Second Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) of Ecuador for 2026-2035 includes mitigation actions related to sustainable mobility aimed at reducing emissions from transport (República del Ecuador, 2025). In this context, the decarbonization of light-duty transport is relevant not only for lowering fossil fuel consumption and direct CO₂ emissions, but also for assessing how the additional electricity demand from transport electrification can be supplied through the cleanest and most efficient energy mix available in Ecuador. The National Electromobility Strategy for Ecuador (ENEM) provides a policy reference for electric vehicle adoption. For the light-duty vehicle segment, ENEM establishes indicative electric vehicle adoption targets for 2025, 2030 and 2040 (MTOPI and BID, 2021). The 2025 target has been nearly achieved when compared with 2024 electric vehicle registration statistics, which are based on administrative records from the National Transit Agency (INEC, 2025). However, achieving the 2030 and 2040 targets will require a significant acceleration in BEVs deployment, together with the expansion of charging infrastructure and enhanced power system readiness. At the same time, recent market trends show that hybrid vehicles currently represent a larger share of electrified assisted vehicle sales than BEVs in Ecuador suggesting that HEVs could play a complementary role during the transition. Although BEV sales grew by 202% between 2024 and 2025, HEVs continued to dominate in absolute terms, with 18,370 units sold compared with 4,276 BEVs (AEADE, 2026). This growth also coincides with Ecuador's 2024 fuel subsidy reform², suggesting that changes in fuel may improve the relative attractiveness of more efficient and low-emission vehicle technologies. This relationship is considered a contextual driver rather than a direct causal effect. Therefore, this study evaluates BEVs as the long-term electrification pathway and HEVs as a complementary transition technology to support emissions reduction while Ecuador scales up sustainable mobility solutions.

2. Methodology

This study uses OSeMOSYS, a bottom-up linear optimization model, to assess alternative pathways for the decarbonization of Ecuador's light-duty transport sector between 2022 and 2050. The model is implemented through MUIO and evaluates how gasoline, diesel, hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs) and battery electric vehicles (BEVs) satisfy light-duty transport demand while interacting with the national power system.

¹ In 2022, the sector emitted 41,674.68 kt CO₂-eq, representing 47.22% of national emissions. Within the sector, transport was the main source of emissions, accounting for 50.83%.

² Presidencia de la República del Ecuador. (2024). *Decreto Ejecutivo No. 308*.

https://www.comunicacion.gob.ec/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/DE_308_20240526132045.pdf

The analysis is guided by three research questions:

- I. What is the potential contribution of Ecuador’s National Electromobility Strategy (ENEM) to the Second NDC 2026–2035 mitigation target?
- II. What is the potential contribution of a combined BEV and HEV transition pathway to Ecuador’s Second NDC 2026–2035 mitigation target?
- III. How would ENEM and BEV–HEV mobility pathways change transport energy demand and electricity supply requirements in Ecuador?

Based on these questions, three scenarios are evaluated:

- **The BAU scenario** is a baseline scenario that explores the least-cost trajectory of Ecuador’s light-duty transport sector under current trends. It considers the existing vehicle fleet structure, observed fuel use patterns, and no additional electrification targets.
- **The ENEM scenario** follows the National Electromobility Strategy for Ecuador, if BEV deployment reaches the ENEM pathway for light-duty vehicles. Hybrid vehicles are included as a complementary transition technology, reflecting recent market trends in Ecuador where HEV adoption remains higher than BEV adoption in absolute terms.
- **The HEV scenario** does not replace the ENEM pathway. Instead, it is included as an alternative transition option to assess the role of hybrid vehicles when BEV deployment follows the historical trend of the registered electric vehicle stock. Under this scenario, BEVs reach around 14% of the ENEM 2030 target, while HEVs play a stronger complementary role in reducing gasoline consumption and direct CO₂ emissions, reflecting possible constraints related to charging infrastructure, market readiness, and electricity supply conditions.

Table 1 provides an overview of the scenarios considered in the analysis and their main assumptions.

Table 1. Scenarios

BAU	ENEM	ENEM + HYBRIDS
Based on the historical behaviour of the registered light-duty vehicle fleet.	BEV deployment follows the ENEM pathway: 5,500 in 2025, 65,000 in 2030 and 590,000 in 2040. HEVs are included as a complementary transition technology.	BEV deployment reaches 14% of the ENEM pathway from 2030 to 2050. HEVs play a stronger transition role under slower BEV deployment.

3. Results and Discussion

The results show that the progressive decarbonization of light-duty transport can contribute to Ecuador’s Second NDC mitigation target. The ENEM and HEV scenarios both result in lower emissions than the BAU scenario by 2035. ENEM shows the highest mitigation potential, driven by the increased adoption of electric and low-emission technologies, reducing emissions by 1.6 ktCO₂e and contributing 15% to the NDC target. HEV also remains below BAU emissions by 0.67 ktCO₂e and contributes with 6%, confirming that hybrid vehicles can serve as a complementary transition technology, particularly where full electrification faces technical, economic, or infrastructure barriers.

Graphic 1. Reduction of light-duty transport Emissions through Lower Fuel Consumption in 2035

Moreover, hydropower remains the main clean energy source in all scenarios. It stays relatively stable between 88.7 PJ in 2022 and around 93.5 PJ between 2030 and 2040, before increasing to 123.9 PJ in 2050 across all scenarios. This indicates that hydropower continues to be the backbone of the renewable electricity system.

Solar energy shows the strongest growth. In 2022 and 2025, solar generation is very low, at around 0.1 PJ. By 2040, solar reaches 35.4 PJ in BAU, 37.4 PJ in ENEM, and 36.1 PJ in HEV. By 2050, it will increase further to 70.6 PJ in BAU, 78.9 PJ in ENEM, and 72.5 PJ in HEV. ENEM has the highest solar expansion, which suggests that higher electrification requires additional renewable electricity generation.

Wind energy increases mainly between 2025 and 2035. It rises from less than 1 PJ in 2025 to around 13.4-13.7 PJ in 2030 and then stabilizes near 15.5-15.7 PJ from 2035 onwards. Compared to solar, wind plays a more complementary role in the modeled energy mix

Graphic 2. Cleaner Electricity Supply to Support Light-Duty Transport Decarbonization (2022-2050)

On the other hand, fuel imports increase in all scenarios between 2022 and 2050, which shows that fossil fuel dependence remains relevant even under transition scenarios. Diesel imports are consistently higher than gasoline imports. In BAU, diesel imports rise from 127.4 PJ in 2022 to 452.5 PJ in 2050, while gasoline imports increase from 95.0 PJ to 327.8 PJ. This represents the highest fossil fuel dependency pathway.

Under ENEM, gasoline imports are significantly lower than BAU in the long term, reaching 260.9 PJ in 2050, compared to 327.8 PJ in BAU. This means ENEM reduces gasoline imports by around 66.9 PJ in 2050, mainly due to stronger BEV deployment. Diesel imports, however, remain high, reaching 449.8 PJ in 2050, very close to BAU.

In addition, the HEV scenario shows an intermediate effect. By 2050, gasoline imports reach 299.9 PJ, which is lower than BAU but higher than ENEM. Diesel imports are also slightly lower than BAU, reaching 441.5 PJ in 2050. This suggests that HEVs can play a complementary transition role, helping reduce fuel demand, but not achieving the same gasoline reduction as stronger electrification.

Graphic 3. Imported Diesel and Gasoline Reduction (2022-2050)

Finally, in terms of cumulative energy demand, the ENEM and HEV scenarios show lower total consumption than BAU over the analysis period. ENEM reaches 5,498.37 PJ and HEV reaches 5,873.74 PJ, compared to 6,257.71 PJ under the BAU scenario. This represents a reduction of 759.34 PJ in ENEM (-12.14%) and 383.97 PJ in HEV (-6.14%) compared to BAU.

Graphic 4. Cumulative Energy Demand and Differences by scenario

4. Conclusion

The modelling results confirm that the decarbonization of Ecuador's light-duty transport sector can make a measurable contribution to the country's Second NDC mitigation target. By 2035, ENEM provides the highest mitigation potential, reducing emissions by 1.60 MtCO₂e and contributing approximately 15% to the NDC target, while the HEV scenario reduces emissions by 0.67 MtCO₂e, equivalent to a 6% contribution. These results show that BEV deployment should remain the main long-term decarbonization pathway, while HEVs can serve as a complementary transition technology, especially while charging infrastructure, affordability, electricity supply readiness and market conditions continue to improve.

The results also show that transport electrification must be closely linked with clean electricity investment. Hydropower remains the backbone of Ecuador's renewable electricity system, increasing from 88.7 PJ in 2022 to 123.9 PJ in 2050. However, solar energy shows the strongest growth, reaching 78.9 PJ in ENEM, 72.5 PJ in HEV, and 70.6 PJ in BAU by 2050. This highlights the need to expand solar generation, strengthen grid flexibility and maintain hydropower reliability to ensure that the mitigation benefits of electric mobility are supported by a cleaner and more diversified electricity supply.

Overall, Ecuador's light-duty transport decarbonization strategy should combine three priorities: accelerating BEV deployment, using HEVs as a complementary transition technology, and linking sustainable mobility policies with energy security objectives. Over 2022–2050, ENEM reduces cumulative energy demand by 759.34 PJ (12.14%) compared with BAU, while HEV reduces it by 383.97 PJ (6.14%). Fuel import results also show that transition pathways can reduce pressure on gasoline imports: by 2050, gasoline imports reach 327.8 PJ under BAU, compared with 260.9 PJ under ENEM and 299.9 PJ under HEV. This integrated approach can help reduce emissions, lower energy demand and decrease dependence on imported fuels.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted Technologies

During the preparation of this work, the authors used AI-assisted tools for language editing and clarity enhancement. The use of these tools did not affect the scientific content, data analysis, or conclusions of the study. The authors reviewed and validated the final manuscript and took full responsibility for its content.

5. References

- República del Ecuador. (2025). *Second Nationally Determined Contribution of the Republic of Ecuador 2026–2035*. United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change.
- Ministerio de Transporte y Obras Públicas, & Banco Interamericano de Desarrollo. (2021). *Estrategia Nacional de Electromovilidad para Ecuador: Consultoría para la elaboración de una Estrategia Nacional de Electromovilidad en Ecuador* [National Electromobility Strategy for Ecuador]. MTOP&BID
- Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos. (2025). *Estadísticas de transporte 2024* [Transport statistics 2024]. INEC.
- Asociación de Empresas Automotrices del Ecuador. (2026). *Boletín de ventas para prensa: Ventas de vehículos – diciembre 2025* [Press sales bulletin: Vehicle sales – December 2025]. AEADE.
- Howells, M., Rogner, H., Strachan, N., Heaps, C., Huntington, H., Kypreos, H., Hughes, A., Silveira, S., DeCarolis, J., Bazillian, M. and Roehrl, A. (2011) OSeMOSYS: The Open Source Energy Modeling System. *Energy Policy*, 39(10), pp. 5850-5870.
-
-

"The views expressed in this material do not necessarily reflect the UK government's official policies."

